

Clinical pharmacist interventions in infectious disease service: types, acceptance, and cost savings analysis using a customized electronic intervention system

Bashayer Alshehail¹

¹ Pharmacy Practice Department, College of Pharmacy, Imam Abdulrahman Bin Faisal University, Dammam, Saudi Arabia

Corresponding author: Bashayer Alshehail (bmalshehail@iau.edu.sa)

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Abstract

Background: Having a dedicated clinical pharmacist (CP) is essential for enhancing antimicrobial use and therapy. This study aimed to evaluate the types of interventions by CPs in infectious disease (ID) cases, focusing on intervention type and cost savings while utilizing and customizing an electronic reporting system.

Methods: A retrospective observational study was conducted on CP interventions in ID service at a tertiary care hospital. The primary objective was to categorize the types of CP interventions used in ID services. Secondary objectives included evaluating the physician acceptance rate and estimating the cost savings achieved through the electronic intervention system.

Results: A total of 464 interventions were performed on 187 patients under the ID consultation service. CPs documented various types of interventions, with the most common being pharmacokinetics (PK) dosing/monitoring (25.9%) and renal dosing (20.7%). These interventions resulted in an estimated cost savings of approximately 234,666 Saudi Riyals (SAR), equivalent to 62,577.60 United States dollars (USD).

Conclusions: Our study confirmed that CP involvement in ID services contributed to cost savings and shortened the length of hospital stay.

Keywords

antimicrobial stewardship, cost saving, electronic intervention system, infectious disease pharmacist, interventions

Introduction

The rising prevalence of antimicrobial resistance, medication-related adverse events, and escalating healthcare costs highlight the urgent need to improve infectious disease (ID) management. Antimicrobial resistance is recognized as a global health threat with high mortality rates,

requiring immediate action to address this issue (Ho et al. 2025). Without implementing corrective measures to optimize antimicrobial use, we could face 10 million deaths worldwide annually by 2050 (Global burden of bacterial antimicrobial resistance 2022). Misuse of antimicrobials – including improper selection, dosing, route, and duration – is a key driver of resistance (Ndaki et al. 2025). Having

a dedicated clinical pharmacist (CP) with specialized ID training is essential for enhancing antimicrobial use and therapy. Clinical pharmacists have become vital members of the ID team, making significant contributions through interventions that improve treatment outcomes, enhance patient safety, and reduce unnecessary costs. Their role is critical in combating antimicrobial resistance (Alsowaida et al. 2022; Dighriri et al. 2023). Many studies have examined the role of ID pharmacists and their interventions (Ijo and Feyerharm 2011; Al-Somai et al. 2014; Zhang et al. 2020; Gu et al. 2023). However, the specific types, acceptance rates, and economic impact of pharmacist-led interventions in ID services remain underexplored in many healthcare settings. This retrospective study aims to evaluate the types of interventions made by clinical pharmacists in ID cases, focusing on intervention type, physician acceptance, and cost savings. Quantifying the impact of pharmacy interventions on cost avoidance is challenging because it involves adjusting for various variables; therefore, many efforts are not accurately documented, as quantification is a complex process. When calculating cost reductions, both direct savings – such as switching from IV to PO – and indirect savings – such as avoiding hospital stays through interventions like switching to a home elastomeric infusion pump for IV antimicrobial therapy – should be considered. An electronic system capable of quantifying pharmacist interventions and translating them into cost savings, tailored to an institution's specific products and metrics, is not widely discussed in the literature. The primary goal of this study was to evaluate the interventions made by a specialized CP within the ID service and their associated cost savings, using and customizing an electronic reporting system. We utilized Quantifi by Wolters Kluwer to document these interventions. It is a customizable application that translates pharmacist interventions into cost savings based on cost avoidance formulas, which are built and configured according to evidence and information provided by the institution regarding the cost of hospital stays, laboratory tests, investigations, and local formulary medications.

Methods

Study design and setting

A retrospective observational study of clinical pharmacist interventions was conducted in the ID service at a tertiary care academic hospital with over 500 beds. Data were collected using the electronic intervention system Quantifi by Wolters Kluwer and patient electronic records over 9 months, from January 2022 to September 2022.

Study population

The study population included all adult patients (aged 18 years or older) who were under the ID service and had a documented intervention by a specialized ID clinical pharmacist. These interventions included antimicrobial

bug/drug mismatch, antimicrobial de-escalation, antimicrobial optimization, discontinuation based on recommended duration, IV-to-PO switch, patient enrollment on a home elastomeric pump, pharmacokinetic (PK) dosing and monitoring, and renal dosing.

Definitions of the type of interventions

Antimicrobial bug/drug mismatch is defined as a patient being treated with an antibiotic that does not target the bacteria identified in cultures (Spivak et al. 2016).

Antimicrobial de-escalation involves discontinuing one or more of the combination antimicrobials used for empirical therapy and/or switching from a broad-spectrum to a narrower-spectrum antimicrobial (De Waele et al. 2020).

Optimization of antimicrobial therapy involves dosing based on patient characteristics (such as weight, age, and renal or liver function), pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic parameters of the drug (such as concentration at the site of action), and the causative microorganisms (Haseeb et al. 2021; Haseeb et al. 2022).

The IV-to-PO switch is defined as either replacing a parenteral medication with its oral form of the same compound or switching from an injectable antimicrobial to an oral agent in a different class or another antimicrobial within the same class, where the frequency, dose, and spectrum of activity might not be the same (Cyriac and James 2014).

Patient enrollment on an elastomeric pump: Patients who require IV antimicrobial therapy and cannot switch to oral treatment – due to the location of the infection site or the resistance pattern of the organism – can be discharged home with an elastomeric pump to continue IV therapy once they are clinically stable. An example of an eligible patient is someone with a complicated urinary tract infection caused by an extended-spectrum beta-lactamase-producing organism and otherwise clinically stable, requiring IV ertapenem. Patient enrollment involves screening for eligible patients, providing patient education and consent, and follow-up throughout the entire antimicrobial course.

PK dosing and monitoring involve personalized dosing aimed at achieving antimicrobial exposures with a high probability of therapeutic success while reducing the risks of toxicity and antimicrobial resistance (Roberts et al. 2012). This method is employed for antimicrobials that require serum measurements, such as vancomycin, aminoglycosides, and voriconazole.

Outcome measures

The primary objective is to categorize and assess the types of clinical pharmacist interventions made in ID services over the defined period. Secondary objectives include evaluating the physician acceptance rate of these interventions, estimating the cost savings associated with accepted pharmacist interventions by using the electronic intervention system, and identifying patterns or trends in interventions linked to greater cost impact.

Cost saving

Cost savings were calculated using two measures: hard costs, which are defined as tangible SAR and USD saved by switching from one drug to another or changing routes, and soft costs, which are intangible and saved by performing an intervention that prevents an extra day's hospital stay. All the intervention types' values were based on multiple studies and literature, taking into consideration the following: hospital length of stay cost (as per our hospital), drug cost based on our local prices, laboratory cost, and time taken to perform the intervention. We used Pharmacy OneSource software service to build the tailored cost savings as per our institutional formulary and utilized their cost avoidance formulas.

Examples of the calculated cost avoidance formula: If an intervention involves therapeutic interchange, the system uses the average cost differential between several commonly interchanged antimicrobials and then applies a "days of therapy impacted" factor to derive the average value of an interchange recommendation. Another example is pharmacokinetic intervention, where drug levels are avoided; in this case, the cost reduction is the average cost of a drug level at our institution, which serves as the intervention value.

For the IV-to-PO switch, we calculate the average cost difference between commonly interchanged IV-and-PO medications, then multiply this difference by a "days of therapy impacted" factor to determine the average value of an IV/PO recommendation. For example, IV Bactrim costs 21 SAR (around 5.6 USD) per day, while oral Bactrim costs 4 SAR (around 1.1 USD) per day. The difference is 17 SAR, which we then multiply by the days of therapy impacted per patient.

Cost analysis and system customization

In our institution, the Quantifi system was customized to reflect hospital-specific costs. Specifically, drug cost-saving formulas were adjusted based on our hospital's acquisition prices from the pharmacy procurement database, and hospitalization-related costs were aligned with the finance department's estimates for daily bed occupancy in general wards and intensive care units. Additionally, laboratory and diagnostic test savings were calculated using data provided by the laboratory department for the cost of each test. While these parameters were tailored to our own setting, the Quantifi platform can be easily adjusted to reflect the cost structures of other institutions, which makes the approach applicable across different healthcare systems once local financial data are incorporated.

Data collection

During the study period, all interventions performed by the ID pharmacist were entered into the pharmacy intervention system, Quantifi by Wolters Kluwer. The information entered included patient identification, consultation service, antimicrobials involved in the intervention, type of intervention, acceptance, and days of therapy impacted. The system then translated each intervention into a cost-saving value based on the literature review and the metrics provided by the drugstore and hospital. The build,

configuration, and validation of the intervention electronic system for clinical intervention information and cost analysis were carried out by two clinical pharmacists, a drug information pharmacist, and an IT pharmacist to ensure accuracy, consistency, and validity. Furthermore, all interventions entered were reviewed by an independent clinical pharmacist and a medication safety pharmacist.

Ethics approval

The research project was approved by the Institutional Review Board (IRB) at Imam Abdulrahman bin Faisal University (IRB-2025-05-0406).

Statistical analysis

Descriptive statistics were used in the study with the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25 (IBM Corporation, Armonk, New York, United States). For categorical data, frequencies and percentages were reported. For continuous variables, mean and standard deviation were used to summarize the data. The chi-square test was used to assess the statistical significance of the association between interventions and outcomes. A p-value less than or equal to 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

A total of 693 interventions were identified in the electronic intervention system; 229 interventions were excluded because the patient's age was under 18 or the interventions occurred outside the ID service. Ultimately, 464 interventions performed on 187 patients, followed by the ID consultation service, were included. Among the included patients, the mean age was 64.2 ± 16.5 years (mean \pm SD). The types of infections in these patients were as follows: urinary tract infections (27.8%), respiratory tract infections (27.3%), skin and soft tissue infections (17.6%), bone/joint infections (6.4%), and others, which included intraabdominal infections, line-related infections, and central nervous system infections (20.9%).

Table 1. Patient baseline characteristics, type of infection, and renal function.

Characteristics	Values
Age (Mean \pm SD, years)	64.2 \pm 16.5
Gender	
Male	79 (42.2%)
Female	108 (57.8%)
Type of infection	
Urinary tract infection	52 (27.8%)
Respiratory infection	51 (27.3%)
Skin/soft tissue infection	33 (17.6%)
Bone/joint	12 (6.4%)
Others	39 (20.9%)
Baseline renal function (median and IQR)	
Serum creatinine (mg/dL)	1.3 (0.6–2.4)
Creatinine clearance (mL/min)	44 (26–98)

SD, standard deviation; IQR, interquartile range.

Table 2. Types, numbers, and cost savings of ID pharmacist interventions.

Intervention type	Number of interventions	Percentage (%)	Cost savings in SAR	Cost savings in USD
Bug/Drug Mismatch	40	8.6	9960	2656.00
Antimicrobial De-escalation	65	14	12940	3450.67
Antimicrobial optimization	48	10.3	8466	2257.60
Discontinuation Of Drug Therapy	39	8.4	5850	1560.00
IV-to-PO switch	27	5.8	3250	866.67
Patient Enrolment on OPAT	29	6.3	151960	40522.67
PK Dosing/Monitoring	120	25.9	28800	7680.00
Renal Dosing	96	20.7	13440	3584.00
Total	464		234,666	62577.60

IV, intravenous; OPAT, outpatient parenteral antimicrobial therapy; PK, pharmacokinetics; PO, by mouth; SAR, Saudi Riyal; USD, United States dollar

The most common interventions by the ID pharmacist (Table 2) included PK dosing/monitoring (25.9%), renal dosing (20.7%), and antimicrobial de-escalation (14%).

Other types of interventions performed were antimicrobial optimization (10.3%), antimicrobial bug/drug mismatch (8.6%), discontinuation of drug therapy (8.4%), patient enrollment on an elastomeric pump (6.3%), and IV-to-PO switch (5.8%). Among the PK dosing/monitoring interventions, the most frequently administered antimicrobials were vancomycin (79%) and gentamicin (21%). Table 3 shows the frequency and percentage of ID clinical pharmacist interventions for each antimicrobial. The antimicrobials with the highest number of interventions (Fig. 1) were meropenem (18%), piperacillin/tazobactam (15%), vancomycin (11%), colistin (10%), and cefepime (5%).

Table 3. Clinical pharmacist intervention frequencies to optimize antimicrobial management per antimicrobial.

Antimicrobial	Clinical pharmacist interventions	
	Number	(%)
Meropenem	83	18.0%
Piperacillin/Tazobactam	70	15.0%
Vancomycin	46	10.0%
Colistin	46	10.0%
Cefepime	23	5.0%
Ceftazidime/Avibactam	19	4.0%
Ertapenem	19	4.0%
Gentamicin	19	4.0%
Ciprofloxacin	19	4.0%
Ceftazidime	14	3.0%
Clindamycin	14	3.0%
Acyclovir	9	2.0%
Amoxicillin/Clavulanate	9	2.0%
Amphotericin B	9	2.0%
Caspofungin	9	2.0%
Linezolid	9	2.0%
Cefazolin	9	2.0%
Amikacin	9	2.0%
Trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole	9	2.0%
Anidulafungin	5	1.0%
Voriconazole	5	1.0%
Azithromycin	5	1.0%
Fluconazole	5	1.0%

For patient enrollment on elastomeric pumps, the most commonly used antimicrobial was ertapenem (87%). The IV-to-PO switch was most frequently performed with ciprofloxacin (22%) and clindamycin (18%). The acceptance rate of the interventions by the ID team was 96%.

Of the 464 interventions, the cost savings calculated using the tailored electronic system totaled 234,666 SAR (around 62,577.6 USD). The intervention with the highest cost savings was patient enrollment on an elastomeric pump, resulting in a savings of 151,960 SAR (around 40,522.7 USD), followed by PK dosing/monitoring (28,800 SAR/7680 USD) and renal dosing (13,440 SAR/3584 USD).

Patients under ID clinical pharmacist review were significantly more likely to have a hospital stay of <10 days compared with those not reviewed (106/187 [57%] vs. 19/50 [38%], $p = 0.025$) (Table 4).

Table 4. Length of hospital stay of patients reviewed vs. not reviewed by the ID clinical pharmacist.

Length of hospital stay (Days)	Patients not reviewed by an ID clinical pharmacist*	Patients under ID clinical pharmacist review	P-value
<10 days	19 (38%)	106 (57%)	0.0187
≥ 10 days	31 (62%)	81(43%)	

* During the clinical pharmacist's leave.

Discussion

Our research highlighted the vital role of the ID clinical pharmacist as an essential member of a multidisciplinary team within the ID service. The ID clinical pharmacists documented various types of interventions, with the most common being PK dosing/monitoring (25.9%), renal dosing (20.7%), and antimicrobial de-escalation (14%). These interventions during the study period resulted in an estimated cost savings of approximately 234,666 SAR (around 62,577.6 USD). The intervention with the highest cost savings was patient enrollment on an elastomeric pump, followed by PK dosing/monitoring and renal dosing. Customizing the intervention electronic system to include cost-saving formulas based on our institution's data helped document and track interventions and easily link them to cost savings. The high acceptance rate (96%) among physicians for these interventions indicates a

Figure 1. Antimicrobials with the highest rates of interventions by the ID clinical pharmacist.

Figure 2. The cost reduction (%) associated with each ID clinical pharmacist intervention.

strong recognition of the value that clinical pharmacists bring to the healthcare team. Many studies have examined the role of pharmacists in ID services and the types of interventions they perform; however, none have explored tools capable of quantifying these interventions in

terms of cost savings. One study by Salman et al. (2015), conducted at a teaching hospital in Oman with a 500-bed capacity similar to our facility, aimed to assess the clinical and financial impact of pharmacist interventions on antimicrobials. The most common intervention was dos-

ing adjustment (42% of total interventions), followed by discontinuation of antimicrobial orders in 34% of cases. This aligns with our observation that PK dosing and monitoring were the most frequently reported interventions (25.9%). That study projected a net annual cost savings of approximately 200,200,000 USD, using a predefined cost avoidance model alongside a direct cost reduction estimate. Unlike our approach, they did not employ an electronic application to standardize formulas and ensure consistency in cost reduction reporting, nor did they document an acceptance rate. Leache et al. (2020) also evaluated the clinical and economic impact of pharmacist interventions on antimicrobials, specifically in critically ill patients. This retrospective observational study included adults admitted to an ICU over five months. A total of 212 drug-related problems were identified in 114 patients, 18 of which involved medication errors. These interventions resulted in a cost reduction of 10,905 euros (around 12,453.5 USD). The physicians accepted 97.6% of the interventions, a rate comparable to the 96% acceptance rate documented in our study. A recent study by Ali Hassan et al. (2021), employing a before-and-after design aimed to evaluate clinical pharmacy and antimicrobial stewardship interventions for ID patients at a tertiary care hospital in Lahore. They documented 136 interventions; physicians accepted 66% of these, which is lower than our acceptance rate. However, the most common interventions involved spectrum-based antibiotic selection and dose de-escalation approaches, also observed in our research, with antimicrobial de-escalation accounting for 14% of interventions and antimicrobial optimization for 10.3%. In another study conducted at Amui Hospital in China, ID pharmacist interventions as part of antimicrobial stewardship activities were examined over 5 years. These interventions led to substantial cost avoidance of 7,631,400 USD, although cost savings were measured solely based on length of stay reduction, unlike our study, which accounted for both tangible and intangible costs.

Our study demonstrated that involvement of an ID clinical pharmacist was associated with a significantly shorter length of hospital stay. Patients who had an ID clinical pharmacist review were more likely to be discharged within 10 days compared with those without a pharmacist review who stayed longer (57% vs. 38%, $p = 0.0187$). One of the reasons for shorter hospital stays is the pharmacist's involvement in the elastomeric home infusion pump. The home infusion pump reduces hospital length of stay; however, it still requires a dedicated education session for the patient and caregiver, in addition to daily follow-up and weekly laboratory testing, which the ID pharmacist leads. Our findings were consistent with previous research, indicating the importance of ID clinical pharmacist interventions, which generally achieve high acceptance rates and yield measurable economic benefits. However, none of these studies explored the development of a customizable electronic system capable of translating interventions into cost savings, considering both hard and

soft costs. Implementing such a system would not only unify and standardize interventions but also save time and ensure continuity in reporting. These cost-saving data could strengthen the pivotal role of ID pharmacists and support the expansion of clinical services. Traditional methods for evaluating clinical pharmacist interventions, such as chart reviews with paper-based documentation, have been widely used but are often labor-intensive, subject to reporting bias, and limited in their ability to capture real-time data. In contrast, the electronic Quantifi system enabled standardized, prospective documentation of interventions, facilitated cost analysis, and allowed for consistent categorization across clinical settings. However, unlike multicenter collaborative databases or validated intervention scoring tools, the system is primarily institution-specific and requires customization of cost parameters. While this enhances accuracy within a given hospital, it may limit direct comparability with studies using other evaluation methods. The system improves internal accuracy but may limit comparability across different institutions. Accordingly, future studies should aim to directly compare Quantifi or similar electronic platforms with established scoring systems to better define their relative advantages and limitations and to support broader applicability across healthcare settings.

Our study has limitations, including a small sample size, a retrospective design, and a focus on an ID subspecialty. It was conducted in a single center with a relatively small sample size, which may limit the generalizability of the findings to other institutions. Additionally, the study period overlapped with the COVID-19 pandemic, during which clinical practices, infection control measures, and antimicrobial use patterns may have been altered. Moreover, although we included outcome data as length of hospital stay, other important outcomes, such as mortality, morbidity, hospital readmissions, and adverse drug events, were not assessed due to data limitations. Accordingly, future research involving different patient populations and larger cohorts may provide more comprehensive insights.

Conclusion

Our study reinforces the need to integrate ID clinical pharmacists into ID services to optimize patient outcomes and achieve cost efficiencies. Continued efforts to document and promote their interventions will be crucial in further establishing their role as vital members of the healthcare team in combating antimicrobial resistance and improving overall healthcare quality. Utilizing electronic systems and customizing them to each institution will help achieve these targets.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The author has declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

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Author contributions

The author solely contributed to this work.

Author ORCIDs

Bashayer Alshehail <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2372-9462>

Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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